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ANALYSIS OF FEATURES OF TECHNOLOGICAL SCHEMES OF PROCESSES OF LASER-PLASMA CUTTING AND WELDING

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Summary: The article shows that the application of the technological scheme of laser-plasma cutting and welding with coaxial summing of both energy sources on one side of the workpiece leads to the appearance of the so-called hybrid effect, which consists in "binding" the anode spot of the arc to the radiation zone, stabilizing its combustion in the hybrid process at currents up to 300 A and reducing the voltage at the arc gap due to the increase of its electrical conductivity due to overheating of the plasma by laser radiation, this allows to significantly increase the speed of cutting and welding processes without increasing the running energy. The use of technological schemes of laser-plasma cutting and welding with an inclined arrangement of both components of the hybrid process, supplied from one side of the workpiece, also leads to a hybrid effect, but it can be less pronounced, and there is a risk of damage to parts of the equipment (for example, optical elements) reflected from the working area radiation.

Keywords: laser-plasma technologies, cutting, welding, technological schemes, hybrid effect, speed increase.

The development of laser-arc (laser-plasma) processes began in the late 1970s. The idea of summing a laser beam and an electric arc for welding, cutting and other types of metal processing in such a way that both heat sources affect the product within the same heating zone belongs to the English scientist Steen (W. M. Steen), who defended his invention alongside patents (for example [1,2]). He proposed methods of welding, cutting, drilling and surface treatment, in which a laser beam is directed to the workpiece and simultaneously to the heat affected zone of laser radiation, an arc is induced between the electrode and the workpiece. Together with other scientists, he also carried out the first experimental studies of the effects of laser-arc (laser-plasma) effects on the metal being processed [3-5] and for the first time industrially applied hybrid welding [6].

The scheme of the first experiments on the study of laser-arc (laser-plasma) processes of welding and cutting metals is shown in Fig.1. According to this

scheme, continuous emission of a CO₂ laser with a diameter of 10 mm and a power up to 2 kW using a KCl lens with a focal length of 75 mm was focused onto the surface of the sample into a spot size 0.25 ... 0.35 mm. In this case, the focused radiation passed through a hole in a copper nozzle 3 mm in diameter in welding experiments or 1 mm in cutting experiments. Through the nozzle of the laser head, helium or oxygen was supplied to the processing area, respectively for welding or for cutting. As an arc power source, an apparatus for non-consumable electrode welding was used to weld in an inert gas at currents up to 250 A (or welding generator for a current up to 400 A complete with an oscillator). The arc torch could be installed both on the same side of the sample, to which the laser beam was directed, and on the opposite side (see Fig. 1). The tungsten electrode of the torch, protected by a stream of argon, in all experiments was the cathode, and the product was the anode.

Fig.1. Schemes of realization of laser-arc processes of welding and cutting with the positioning of the laser beam and arc with a non-consumable electrode from one side of the product (a) and from different sides (b) [5].

In the implementation of laser-arc processes of welding and cutting, the following effects were noted [5]. If both heat sources were located on the same side of the product, the electric resistance of the arc in the steady-state burning mode (current 100 A) under the influence of laser radiation decreased, as evidenced by a decrease in the voltage across the arc gap while increasing the current. In addition, the anode region of the arc was “binded” to the plasma torch created above the metal surface by a laser beam. At lower currents (70 A), the unstable arc burning associated with the migration of the anode spot was replaced by stable owing to the stabilization of its anodic region in the zone of influence of the laser radiation on the sample. The latter effect was also observed in the case when heat sources were located on different sides of the product, provided that the temperature of the metal under the laser heating spot was not less than 400 K higher than the temperature of the surrounding surface.

The effects of “binding” the anode spot of the arc and stabilizing its burning in the combined process,

even at low currents, made it possible to significantly increase the welding speed compared to not only the arc, but also the laser. In the future, this phenomenon was called the "hybrid effect." Figure 2 shows the dependences of the welding speed on the arc current with full penetration of samples from different metals (the values of laser power are shown in the figure). The greatest increase in speed (in 4 times) was observed when welding low-carbon steel with a thickness of 0.2 mm (curve b) according to the scheme with the location of the arc and laser beam from different sides of the product. More modest results (approximately 2 times increase in speed) were obtained for titanium with a thickness of 0.8 mm (curves a) and low-carbon steel with a thickness of 2 mm with the arc and laser beam on one side of the product. In the latter case, another important effect was observed, namely the absence of undercuts characteristic of high-speed arc welding.

Fig.2. The dependence of the speed of laser-arc welding on the arc current: (a) titanium with a thickness of 0.8 mm at the positioning of the laser beam and the arc from one side of the sample; (b) - low-carbon steel with a thickness of 0.2 mm at the positioning of heat sources from different sides [3].

A significant increase in the processing speed as compared to laser was achieved in experiments on laser-arc cutting of low-carbon steel 3 mm thick with the positioning of the laser beam and arc from opposite sides of the product. Figure 3 shows the dependence of the cutting speed on the amount of thermal energy introduced into the metal. Until the increase in heat input to the product due to the arc did not reach a value approximately equal to the thermal contribution from laser radiation (1870 W), the slope of the experimental curve did not change, and the cutting occurred as if the laser power had simply increased. At the same time, the

quality of the cut was preserved and remained comparable to the quality of conventional laser cutting. Above the specified input power limit (≈ 3800 W), the cutting speed growth slowed down, and the cut quality deteriorated markedly — the cut stop to be parallel and expanded from the arc side due to arc melting of its sides. Under the influence of both heat sources from one side of the product, it was also not possible to achieve high-quality cutting due to the migration of the arc along the cut edges.

Fig.3. The dependence of the cutting speed of low-carbon steel with a thickness of 3 mm on the power introduced into the product (power input up to 1870 W is provided only by a laser beam, and above the specified value - by a laser beam and an electric arc) [5].

In [3, 5], the authors explain the phenomenon of “binding” of the anode area of the arc to the place of laser radiation action by the fact that with a one-sided positioning of heat sources, the arc behaves in accordance with the Steenbeck minimum principle (M. Steenbeck), namely: since the electrical conductivity of the laser plasma which temperature can reach 20000 K is much higher than the electrical conductivity of the surrounding cold gas, the torch of a laser plasma is the preferred, energetically advantageous area of arc burning. The interaction of laser radiation occurring with the near-anode arc plasma leads to an increase in its temperature and, consequently, to electrical conductivity. This circumstance is the reason for the decrease in voltage across the arc gap noted in [3, 5].

In addition, in [3, 5], it is stated that the effect of “binding” the anode region of the arc discharge to the laser heating spot appears at low and medium arc currents (less than 300 A). At high currents, this effect may disappear, which is connected, according to the authors,

with arc self-stabilization due to a powerful cathode jet, in the presence of which the anode spot can move independently of the heating zone created by the laser beam. This is considered as one of the reasons for the deterioration of the quality of hybrid laser-plasma cutting with increasing arc current [5]. In works [3, 5, 7], it is also suggested that an increase in the arc current can lead to an undesirable effect in the case when the “binding” of the anode region of the arc to the torch of the laser plasma does not disappear. This is the reflection effect of a dense plasma laser beam, which is observed with an increase in the electron density in the subsurface plasma above the critical value ($n_e \approx 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ for the plasma to fully reflect the CO_2 -laser radiation) and limits the heat input to the metal to be processed. The authors of these works consider this effect insignificant at arc currents less than 300 A.

When the arc and the laser beam are positioned from different sides of the product, the stabilization of the anode spot in the laser heating zone of the metal will

not lead to a decrease in the arc voltage (see Fig. 1, b) due to the lack of direct interaction of the laser beam with the arc plasma. Therefore, in the future, for the implementation of laser-plasma welding and cutting processes, technological schemes were adopted in which laser radiation and a direct-acting arc are fed from one side of the product (see Fig. 1, a).

Further works on laser-plasma welding of steels and aluminum alloys according to the adopted scheme confirmed the appearance of the hybrid effect. For example, in [8, 9], graphs of the depth of penetration of samples from aluminum alloys on the welding speed for laser, plasma, and hybrid laser-plasma processes are presented. It is shown that the curves constructed by summing the depths of the laser and plasma penetrations are located below the curves constructed from the depths of the hybrid laser-plasma penetration, which vividly illustrates the appearance of the hybrid effect. In the case of the use of CO₂-laser radiation in experiments, this effect provided an increase in the penetration depth of 50 ... 150% (or more), while using a diode one - 25 ... 30%. At the same time, an important advantage of laser-plasma welding over laser welding is the use of the phenomenon of cathodic cleaning of the

surface of aluminum alloys from oxide films [10, 11]. In [12, 13], it was shown that in hybrid laser-plasma welding of thin-sheet (up to 4 mm) stainless steels of both austenitic and ferritic classes, due to the appearance of the hybrid effect with close energy deposition rates, the process can be 2-3 times exceed the speed of laser welding and up to 4 times the speed of the plasma.

To implement the processes of laser-plasma welding, a focused laser beam can be directed to the point of interaction with the material perpendicular to the tangent to the surface of the product being welded at this point (Fig. 4) (for example, [14, 15]), or under a small (up to 8 -12°) angle (Fig.5) (for example, [16]). Structurally, a laser-plasma welding head can consist of separate elements - a laser focusing system and a plasma torch, or be integrated in a common case (Fig. 5). A plasma torch is usually inclined at a certain (minimum possible) angle to the axis of the focused laser beam (Fig. 6) [17]. The filler wire may be fed coaxially with the plasma jet, towards it (Fig. 7), or not at all. Also, powders of metals and alloys can be used as filler materials [18].

Fig.4. The designs of integrated plasma torches that allow laser radiation to be fed coaxially and perpendicular to the surface of the product being welded: a) with a hollow cathode [14]; b) - with inclined cathodes symmetrically located with respect to the axis of the laser beam [15]; c) - the appearance of the plasma torch, made according to scheme (b).

In laser-plasma welding processes, a laser beam with a high power density and an arc plasma with a high energy efficiency interact simultaneously in the weld pool area. To enhance the effect of this interaction, it is advisable to bring them to the welded parts through a common nozzle (Fig. 8). In this case, in all cases, the laser beam relative to the plasma can be located behind or in front along the welding process [19]. In any case, with this arrangement of the beam, there is a danger of

its reflection from the front or rear wall of the vapor-gas channel and penetration of reflected radiation into the optical path, which can lead to the destruction of some optical elements (for example, the output end of an optical fiber transporting laser radiation) [20]. One way to eliminate this drawback is to use a coaxial arrangement of radiation in the integrated plasma torch (Fig. 7).

Fig.5. The designs of hybrid laser-plasma welding heads, in which the laser focusing system and the plasma torch: a) are used separately, or b) integrated in a common housing [16].

Fig.6. The process of hybrid laser-plasma welding with an inclined arrangement of plasma torch, allowing to change the distance between the plasma and the laser beam [17]: a) - appearance of the hybrid laser-plasma welding head; b) - technological scheme of the process.

Fig.7. Dual-cathode integrated plasma torch with coaxial supply of radiation: 1 - radiation input unit; 2 - focusing system; 3 - cathode nodes; 4 - counter feed filler wire; 5 - gas protection of the welded joint.

Fig.8. Diagrams of the process of hybrid laser-plasma welding with the location of the plasma torch in front of (a) and behind (b) a laser beam [19]: 1 - focused laser radiation; 2 - non-consumable electrode; 3 - plasma-forming nozzle; 4 - protective gas; 5 - plasma discharge; 6 - welding pool; 7 - weld metal; 8 - base metal.

In [21, 22], disadvantages in the formation of welds were analyzed in the case of applying the technological scheme of laser-plasma welding with an inclined arrangement of both components of the hybrid process supplied from one side of the welded samples of aluminum alloys. In our opinion, one of the important factors contributing to the minimization or

complete elimination of such disadvantages as the formation of undercuts, sagging of the weld, asymmetry of its formation and the formation of internal pores may be the use of a technological scheme with one-sided coaxial supply of both energy sources.

In addition to the choice of the technological scheme of the laser-plasma process, it is advisable to take into account a number of technological and design

factors. For example, to increase the depth of penetration, it is recommended to use short-focus optics, which allows reducing the size of the focal spot [23]. When using fiber lasers for hybrid welding, increasing the radiation power and reducing the size of the focal spot increases the efficiency of the process, as with other types of lasers. In this case, an increase in the radiation power reduces the welding current, but does not affect the voltage across the arc [24]. The work [25] analyzes the difference between hybrid laser-TIG welding processes when using CO₂ and Yb: YAG lasers in them, i.e. radiation with wavelengths of 10.6 and 1.03 microns, respectively. It is shown that with a decrease in the wavelength, the absorption and refraction of laser radiation in an arc plasma decreases.

In the field of industrial laser-plasma cutting of metals, today a combined technological scheme of the process is used, in which metals with a thickness up to 6-10 mm are cut by laser radiation, and more than that - by a plasma method. In addition, plasma cutting is used in a combined process on extended sections of a direct cut, or in the absence of the need to perform precise and complex elements, in the case of increased requirements for cutting accuracy, laser cutting is used (Fig. 9). A similar approach has been applied in a number of similar designs (for example, [26-29]). This approach to the layout of the equipment provides cutting speeds up to 3000 inches per minute.

To obtain the greatest effect from the joint use of laser and plasma, specialists from the Institute of Manufacturing Technology together with specialists from

Fraunhofer IWS Dresden (Dresden, Germany) developed a hybrid laser-plasma head (Fig. 10) [30]. This head is designed for a laser power of up to 100 W and a welding current of up to 40 A and is designed for micro-welding and cutting of metals of small thickness.

According to the authors, in the processes of laser-plasma cutting on direct polarity, the main condition for the appearance of the hybrid effect is stabilization of the position of the anode spot on the leading front of the cut by acting on it with focused radiation (Fig. 11 a). Such an approach can help increase the speed of cutting or cutting thicker metal sheets. To test this assumption in the E.O. Paton Electric Welding Institute the stand shown in Fig. 11 (b) was developed, on which experiments on laser-plasma cutting were conducted [31]. The data obtained in the course of these experiments suggest that the presence of a hybrid effect during laser-plasma cutting allows a 30-50% increase in cutting speed as compared to the laser at approximately equal heat input of both processes (Fig. 12).

The conducted research allows formulating the following main advantages of hybrid laser-plasma cutting compared to laser cutting:

- summing of laser energy and plasma, allowing to reduce the laser power and reduce the cost of equipment;
- increase productivity by increasing the effective efficiency of the process.

Fig.9. Installation METAL MASTER XCEL FIBER LASER / PLASMA COMBINATION firm Fox Machinery Associates, Inc. (USA) [20].

Fig.10. Head for laser-plasma micro-welding and cutting of metals of small thickness (radiation power 100 W, welding current 40 A) [29].

The main disadvantage of hybrid laser-plasma cutting with an inclined arrangement of laser radiation (with separate use of plasma and laser heads, or an integrated head in which laser radiation is fed at an angle) is the need for a certain spatial orientation of the cutting

tool during operation. I.e. when cutting along an arbitrary path, the cutting tool must always be positioned so as to ensure the condition of appearance of the hybrid effect shown in Fig. 11 (a).

Fig.11. Laser-plasma cutting on direct polarity with an inclined arrangement of laser radiation: a) - the condition for the occurrence of the hybrid effect - “binding” of the plasma of direct action by laser radiation to the leading front of the cut; b) - experimental stand for hybrid cutting.

Fig.12. Dependence of the speed (m / min) of laser and hybrid laser-plasma cutting of carbon steel on the thickness (mm) of the sheet being cut

To eliminate this drawback, it is advisable to use an integrated plasma torch with a coaxial arrangement of laser radiation (Fig. 13). Such a cutting tool due to the coaxial action of laser radiation and plasma of direct polarity will ensure the emergence of a hybrid effect (Fig. 13 a), which will lead to an increase in the quality of the cut by aligning the cutting front compared to the

inclined arrangement of laser radiation, as well as increasing the thickness of the cut material without deterioration of the surface quality of the cut edges. At present, the E.O. Paton Electric Welding Institute is working to create a universal integrated coaxial plasma torch for cutting and welding, based on this approach (Fig. 13, b).

Fig.13. Laser-plasma cutting in direct polarity with coaxial arrangement of direct-acting plasma and laser radiation: a) - leveling the cutting front (quality improvement) when a hybrid effect occurs; b) - universal integrated head for cutting and welding.

Conclusions:

1. The application of the technological scheme of laser-plasma cutting and welding with coaxial supply of both energy sources from one side of the workpiece leads to the appearance of the so-called hybrid effect, which consists in “binding” the anode arc spot to the radiation coverage area, stabilizing its burning in the hybrid process at currents up to 300 A and a decrease in the voltage across the arc gap due to an increase in its electrical conductivity due to overheating of the plasma by laser radiation, which allows a significant increase in the rate of cutting and welding without increasing heat input.

2. The use of technological schemes of laser-plasma cutting and welding with an inclined arrangement of both components of the hybrid process, fed from one side of the workpiece, also leads to the appearance of a hybrid effect, but it may be less expressed, and also there is a danger of damage to equipment parts (for example, optical elements) radiation reflected from the working area.

3. The occurrence of a hybrid effect in laser-plasma welding of aluminum alloys provides an increase in the penetration depth (as compared with the sum of penetration depths from individual components) by 50 ... 150% (and more) in the case of using CO₂-laser radiation and by 25 ... 30% with using a diode laser. In the case of laser-plasma welding of austenitic and ferritic-grade stainless steels up to 4 mm thick, the

same effect leads to an increase in speed by 2-3 times compared to laser welding and up to 4 times compared to plasma welding at close energy costs.

4. The presence of the hybrid effect in laser-plasma cutting allows a 30-50% increase in speed compared to laser cutting at approximately equal heat input of both processes.

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